

Appendix

Table 1 - Main research questions pose in the survey.

Research Question	Purpose
RQ1: What is the perception of experts on uncertainty in self-adaptive systems?	We pose this research question to better understand how experts define uncertainty and its sources in self-adaptive systems.
RQ2: What approaches do experts use to mitigate uncertainty and tackle specific sources of uncertainty in practice?	We pose this research question to get an overview of existing approaches dealing with uncertainty. With this question we aim at: 1) identifying the most common approaches used to resolve uncertainty, 2) identifying the sources of uncertainty for which the approaches are used, 3) investigating whether the approach is used during design-time and/or run-time, and 4) whether or not uncertainty is handled in a systematic or ad-hoc manner.
RQ3: How do existing approaches handle non-functional requirements ¹ and their trade-offs?	We pose this question to investigate how current approaches tackling uncertainty treat quality concerns of the system: 1) whether or not non-functional requirements and their trade-offs are taken into account, and 2) if/how quality assurance is supported after adaptation.

Table 2 - Sub-questions of the first research question of the questionnaire.

ID	Sub-questions of RQ.1
RQ.1.0	Do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "If uncertainty did not exist, there would be no need for self-adaptive systems."
RQ.1.1	How do you define uncertainty in the context of self-adaptive systems? What are the two most common sources of uncertainty that you encountered when developing/evaluating self-adaptive systems?
RQ. 1.2	Do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "Self-adaptive systems tend to face certain sources of uncertainty more often than others". If your response is agree, which types of sources? Please explain your answer.

¹ Note that in this work we use quality concerns, and non-functional requirements interchangeably.

Table 3 - Sub-questions of the second research question of the questionnaire.

ID	Sub-questions of RQ.2
RQ.2.1.	While dealing with uncertainty, do you think it should be tackled at design-time or run-time?
RQ.2.2.	When engineering self-adaptive systems, do you apply particular approaches to mitigate uncertainty? If your answer is yes, please explain what are the sources of uncertainty and the mitigation approach(es) applied.
RQ.2.3.	Continue on your answer to the previous question, are these sources of uncertainty addressed in a systematic way (i.e., using a structured well-defined approach) or ad-hoc (i.e., on a case by case basis)? If your answer is 'systematic', give one or two examples. If your answer is 'ad-hoc' can you explain briefly whether and how this needs to be improved?
RQ.2.4.	Consider a scenario in which a self-adaptive system needs to deal with several sources of uncertainty. When dealing with such multiple sources of uncertainty would you prioritise them? If your answer is yes, please select an option ² or explain your answer.

Table 4 - Sub-questions of the third research question of the questionnaire.

ID	Sub-questions of RQ.3
RQ.3.1	While tackling uncertainty in your work, do you explicitly investigate how non-functional requirements of the system will be affected? If your answer is no, please motivate why not. If your answer is yes, please explain how you achieve this.
RQ.3.2.	When dealing with uncertainty in the self-adaptive systems you have been developing, do you use any method to provide evidence that the system satisfies its stated functional and non-functional requirements under uncertainty? If your answer is yes, please explain what methods you use.

² Respondents could select from the following options: a.The first identified source of uncertainty is handled first (i.e., first come first serve), b.The source of uncertainty with a higher impact on the overall utility of the system gets a higher priority, c. The uncertainty with a higher impact on specific non-functional requirements gets a higher priority, d. The uncertainty with a higher impact on specific system functionality gets a higher priority, e. other (free text).

Table 5- Identified approaches applied during uncertainty handling process.

Approaches	Examples
Requirement-based	Violations of requirements are identified and linked to reconfiguration strategies to handle uncertainty.
Architectural solutions	Effective software design patterns and architectural patterns are used to deal with uncertainty.
Composite solutions (i.e., solutions consisting of more than one technique)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use of a Bayesian backbone to support reasoning and propagation of uncertainty. 2. Composition of "building block" algorithms. 3. Using a systematic safety engineering approach, typically using assurance cases. 4. Identify and verifying adaptation strategies to prevent violation of security, maximizing the satisfaction of security and minimizing the risks. 5. Performing series of activities including: Observation of self-capabilities, providing concurrent watchdogs, activating integrity fences, use of reflective architecture analysis and modification at run time. 6. Run-time adaptation within adaptation space defined at design-time, and based on the monitored events; and/or, run-time adaptation without knowledge of adaptation space and based on symbolic learning of suitable adaptations.
Monitoring parameters	Input measurements from sensors are monitored for optimization purposes.
Scenario-based	Sampling possible outcomes of a stochastic parameter, and then use of outcomes in stochastic optimization.
Machine learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Learning and self-stabilization algorithms, and (b) Phrasing the uncertainty as a reinforcement learning problem (i.e., unknown transitions or probabilities of the underlying MDP).
Model-based	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Approaches with an emphasis on modeling the system, environment and the uncertainty. (b) By modeling uncertainty at design-time, and systematically tracing uncertainty through the different models that are created during development.

Table 6 – Participants’ suggestions to enhance uncertainty handling process, and identified areas for improvement.

Areas for improvement	<p>-Lack of systematic methods to analyze environmental changes.</p> <p>-Lack of generic systematic methods on how to handle different types of sources of uncertainty.</p> <p>-Lack of systematic methods for handling unforeseeable and unmeasurable sources of uncertainty.</p>
Suggested solutions	<p>-A checklist of things that may fail in the system and generic guidelines on how to deal with them.</p> <p>-A catalogue of common systematic approaches to handle sources of uncertainty for specific domains.</p>

Table 7 - Identified design-time and run-time activities and their respective descriptions.

ID	Activity	Description
Design-time		
DTA1	Defining uncertainty	This activity involves defining uncertainty in terms of its characteristics (i.e., nature, location, level, emerging time, and sources) where applicable.
DTA2	Defining goals of uncertainty management process	This activity consists of defining thresholds that need to be met, prioritization of sources (weights) based on their importance and level of impact on the behavior of the system, determining the QAs requiring attention due to application of adaptation uncertainty including QAs goals (i.e., quality attributes that are the goal of adaptation) and the rest of system QAs, and defining optimality in terms of cost-benefit-uncertainty.
DTA3	Identification of sources of uncertainty	This activity includes pinpointing the sources of which are more likely to change over time and need to be monitored.
DTA4	Model uncertainty	This activity includes using modeling techniques to model the system and its environment in order to monitor and predict how it may behave in the future.
DTA5	Capturing external behavior	This activity includes identification of variable parameters locating in the environment or originating from human interactions with the system.
DTA6	Anticipate exceptions and trade-offs	This activity includes identification of potential exceptions , based on the available knowledge, that may affect systems goals (e.g., cost,

		benefit, quality assurances, etc.) in the future, and proposing solutions/trade-offs.
Run-time		
RTA1	Modification of system internal objects	This activity refers to changes required to be applied to the managing system at the implementation level.
RTA2	Uncertainty propagation control	This activity consists of tracing how uncertainty characteristics evolve over time.
RTA3	Use AI solutions	This activity refers to use of artificial intelligence methods (i.e., machine learning) to improve and extend the self-adaptation capabilities based on real life data collected throughout the life cycle of the system.
RTA4	Collect real life parameters	This activity refers to collection of external and/or internal parameters which are required in any of the previous activities.